

A STUDY ON EFFECT OF COVID-19 ON EDUCATION OF DEGREE COLLEGE STUDENTS IN DOMBIVLI CITY

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Abstract:

Education all over the world has been affected directly or indirectly to Covid-19 pandemic. Within a short span of time the outlook of the entire stakeholder in the education industry has changed. There is a paradigm shift from offline teaching to online teaching. Though new, the teachers and the students both have adapted with online system with its pros and cons. This paper studies the effect of Covid-19 on the education in general and degree college students of Commerce stream of Dombivli in particular. The objective of this research paper is to know about the Covid-19 pandemic and to study the effect of Covid-19 on education of degree college students. This research paper is descriptive and analytical in nature. The data collected were both primary and secondary data. The testing of null hypothesis was done by using ANOVA. Key findings and suggestions form a part of the research paper.

Keywords: Education, Covid-19, Effect, Degree College, Students.

Introduction

The COVID-19 Pandemic in the year 2019-2020 hit hard to the entire sector and left an adverse impact on economic and human life. WHO declared Covid-19 a pandemic on 12th March, 2020. The spread of this virus already started in China when first case of someone suffering from Covid-19 traced back to 17th November 2019 according to media reports on unpublished Chinese government data. Most of the countries were unaware about the spread of virus in the initial stage. The situation of lockdown, quarantine and restrictions have been implemented around the world. By April 2020 half of the world's population were under lockdown reducing human loss was more important than saving economic during the spread. Government of India announced nationwide lockdown on 24th march for 21 days which keeps on extending depending on situation. The lockdown situation leads to panic situation people were rushing to stock essential in some part all the services were restricted except essential services. The highest case peaked in India was on 17th September 2020 (Times of India). Covid-19 cases in India as on 22, Feb 2021 Active cases 150055 Discharged 10699 410, Deaths 156385 (Ministry of health and family welfare) Most of the government had decided to temporarily close educational institutions in an attempt to reduce the spread of Covid-19 as of 12 January, 2021 approximately 825 millions learners are currently affected due to school closures. On 16th march India declared a country wide lockdown of schools and colleges Education sector was the first Sector to be impacted by current Pandemic. 19th March the UGC (University Grant Commission) asked Universities to postpone exams until March 31. The exams of CBSE and ICSE board postponed till 31 March at first and then until July. Maharashtra government cancelled examinations for class 1 to 8 and promoted the students to next class examination for class IX and XI were

also post ponded. Most of the states in India have post ponded the exams or cancelled the examinations to slow down the spread of virus. During 1918 - 1919 Influenza pandemic in US, school closures and public gatherings were bans which resulted lower mortality rates. Those who have implemented such steps at early stage had greater delay in reaching peak mortality rates. Multiple countries successfully slowed the spread of infection through school closure during 2009 H1N1 Flu Pandemic. School closure is not the only solution to slow down the spread of virus maintains social distancing and other preventive steps to be followed.

Review of Literature

The Impact of COVID-19 on Education in Ghana Joshua-Luther Ndoye Upoalkpajor1* and Cornelius Bawa Upoalkpajor2, This study was intended to examine the effect of COVID-19 on education in Ghana. This study was guided by the following objectives; to evaluate the awareness of COVID-19 virus among students in Ghana, to examine the impact of COVID-19 on education in Ghana and to evaluate the after effect of COVID-19 epidemic on education system in Ghana. It concluded that the focus of current activities is on providing information and preventing the spread of the epidemic. These are important and should not be neglected. Equal importance must be placed on the more difficult tasks associated with planning for the impacts which will impede the Ministry's ability to deliver education. In addition, now that the impacts on the education system itself are better understood, the programme of activities must include planning for the impacts on the demand for education and the ability of the Ministry to supply education.

Online Learning Readiness Among University Students in Malaysia Amidst Covid-19 Ellen Chung1*, Geetha Subramaniam2, Laura Christ Dass3, This paper sets out to examine online learning readiness among university students who have been thrown in at the deep end. It aims to investigate if demographic factors make any difference in their readiness to learn, online learning experiences and intention to continue using online learning. It also examines their preferred methods of online learning and challenges they face, it concluded that as for ways to improve understanding of subject matter, the university needs to organise more training sessions to equip lecturers to be more effective in delivering online learning contents. Synchronisation of online platforms used for online teaching and learning by the university is necessary to avoid problems of students having to deal with different platforms used by lecturers of different subjects. This may go a long way to help alleviate students' anxiety in reference to online learning

Emergency Online Learning (EOL) during the COVID-19 pandemic: Postgraduate students' perspectives Upasana Singh, Cecile Gerwel Proches, Cristy Leask, Craig Blewett, This study, therefore, set out to investigate how Commerce postgraduate coursework students in a College at a large University in South Africa, experienced a rapid shift from fully face-to-face teaching to fully EOL. This study was quantitative with data collected through an online questionnaire. The research revealed that these students find that there are no boundaries between their studies, home, and work-life. They experienced challenges with time management, and concerns about future employment and personal financial worries also impacted their academic studies. In terms of support, the elements of support from lecturers as well as the support from course administrators are really important in online learning. This research contributes to the specific focus area of online learning among coursework postgraduate students.

The review of literature was done of various related topics but few have been incorporated here. The rest gets incorporated in the references. The research gap was identified and accordingly the study was conducted for degree college students in Dombivli city.

Rationale of the Study

Only a handful of schools and universities have succeeded in adopting such methods mostly in urban and metro cities. The low income private and government sectors are quite inefficient to adopt such method resulting in shutdown. Colleges of metro cities and urban areas are somehow assumed to be less impacted as compared to colleges of rural area. The city of Dombivli is selected for the purpose of the study as it is a combination of urban and rural divide; more so, it is known as a literate city or the city of knowledge and education not only in Thane District but in Maharashtra State. Given the fact, there was a need to understand the teaching-learning satisfaction in higher education and therefore degree college students in commerce became the respondents for the study.

Objectives of Study

- To know about the Covid-19 pandemic
- To study the effect of Covid-19 on education of degree college students

Hypotheses

H₀ -There is no significant difference between gender and online learning.

H₀ -There is no significant difference between colleges and online learning satisfaction of students. .

Research Methodology

Data Collection: Both Primary & Secondary data was collected. Primary data was collected by floating the structured questionnaire on Google form. The questionnaire was framed with 09 questions with five point Likert scale and 02 open-ended questions along with demographic questions. The Secondary data was collected from articles in journals and official websites of WHO, Maharashtra Government and Central Government.

Population and Sample: The population covered the students in degree colleges in the city of Dombivli. There are 10 degree colleges affiliated to the University of Mumbai with approximately 10000 students. The population for the study were all the Ten degree colleges in Dombivli, Census method was applied for colleges. 150 students comprising of 15 students of 10 colleges were taken by stratified random sampling method.. The KMO test was conducted to check the data adequacy.

Data Processing: The steps of data processing was followed. The questionnaire was subject to editing, incomplete questionnaires were removed and complete questionnaires were taken into consideration which resulted into 150 responses. It was classified and tabulated and summarized and gets incorporated in the flow of the paper.

The **Data Analysis** was done through qualitative and quantitative analysis. Qualitative analysis was done by finding the average percentage/ Mean to understand the opinion of the respondents which are reflected in the findings. The detail table-wise analysis is not given due to limitations of words in the paper. The quantitative analysis was done by using the SPSS package. The test of normality was done by KS-Shapiro-Wilk test. For the first set of null hypothesis, the data was found to be in non-normal pattern and therefore the null hypotheses were tested by using non parametric test through Mann-Whitney U Test, which is similar to t test in parametric test. For the Second set of null hypothesis, the data was found to be in normal pattern and therefore the null hypotheses were tested by using parametric test through ANOVA Test The testing of null and alternate hypotheses gets reported in detail in data analysis.

Scope of the Study

- This paper covers degree college commerce students only.
- The study covers students from Dombivli city Thane Maharashtra India.

- The colleges covered were: Pragati College of Arts and Commerce, K.V Pendharkar College, Model College, Manjunath College, G.R Patil College, Vande Mataram College, NFAS Degree College, SIA College, Swami Vivekanand College and K.M Patel College.

Limitations of study

The paper does not cover junior college and other streams/programmes

The paper does not cover teachers' level of satisfaction for online teaching-learning

Contribution of Research

The research paper contributes to the different attributes of on-line teaching-learning, their expectations, their willingness and their level of satisfaction. In this era of technology sooner or later the teaching methodologies will have to be properly blended and optimally utilized and therefore it's the need of the hour to understand their satisfaction, expectation and perception, which in turn will have the teachers in general to activate and improvise upon the teaching in general and the students learning in particular.

Data Analysis

The data analysis was done by using the SPSS package. The questionnaire was framed with with five point Likert scale. The data analysis was considering all the questions. The questions asked were related to different facilities expected by the students from their respective colleges. The detail of qualitative analysis is given in the findings.

The reliability test - Cronbach's Alpha was done to find out whether the data is reliable or not. The results are as follows

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.847	5

It was observed from the above table the alpha coefficient for five items is .839, suggesting that the items have relatively high internal consistency.

Five statements: -

1. Level of satisfaction with online learning.
2. Use of PPTs during online lectures by teachers
3. Level of comfort towards online completion of Syllabus
4. Use of virtual white board in online teaching
5. Supportive home environment in online learning.

It was pertinent to check the whether the data was adequate. The KMO and Bartlett's Test was conducted for the same and it was accepted hence data is adequate.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.884
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	351.315
	df	21
	Sig.	.000

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The KMO statistic varies between 0 and 1.

Normality Testing
For the first set of null hypotheses – Gender and variables

 H₀: - Distribution is Normal

 H₁: - Distribution is Non-Normal

Tests of Normality

	Gender	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Covid-19 affected the ability to learn	Female	.230	92	.000	.894	92	.000
	Male	.227	58	.000	.893	58	.000
I wish to continue offline learning	Female	.177	92	.000	.915	92	.000
	Male	.190	58	.000	.897	58	.000
Use of PPTs by teacher is beneficial	Female	.294	92	.000	.841	92	.000
	Male	.332	58	.000	.805	58	.000
Use of Virtual white board during online teaching	Female	.301	92	.000	.841	92	.000
	Male	.295	58	.000	.805	58	.000
Comfortable with online learning syllabus	Female	.283	92	.000	.872	92	.000
	Male	.308	58	.000	.821	58	.000
My home environment supports online learning	Female	.276	92	.000	.851	92	.000
	Male	.305	58	.000	.837	58	.000
Level of Satisfaction with online learning	Female	.213	92	.000	.886	92	.000
	Male	.270	58	.000	.870	58	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

It was observed from the data Sig. value for all the factors was less than 0.05, which means the null hypothesis is rejected and it can be concluded that the given data is Non-Normal and hence no parametric test was used for testing of null hypotheses so the relevant Non-Parametric test – Mann-Whitney U test was applied.

For the Second null hypothesis – Colleges and level of students' satisfaction

 H₀: - Distribution is Normal

 H₁: - Distribution is Non-Normal

Test of Normality

	Name of College	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Level of Satisfaction with online learning	Pragati College of Arts and Commerce	.257	15	.009	.884	15	.055
	K.V Pendharkar College	.300	15	.001	.814	15	.006
	Model College	.292	15	.001	.849	15	.017
	Manjunath College	.219	15	.052	.914	15	.154
	G.R Patil College	.258	15	.008	.882	15	.050
	Vande Mataram College	.266	15	.005	.890	15	.068
	NAFS Degree College	.268	15	.005	.861	15	.025
	SIA College	.221	15	.048	.865	15	.029
	Swami Vivekanand College	.249	15	.013	.806	15	.004
	K.M Patel College	.200	15	.110	.868	15	.032

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

It can be observed from the data Sig. value for all the factors was greater than 0.05 as per the Shapiro-Wilk test, which means the null hypothesis is accepted and it can be concluded that the given data is Normal and hence parametric test – ANOVA Test was used for testing of null hypotheses.

Testing of Hypotheses

I For the first set of null hypotheses – Gender and variables

Null hypothesis	Summary	Result										
here is no significant relationship between Gender and level of satisfaction with online learning	<p style="text-align: center;">Hypothesis Test Summary</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;"></th> <th style="width: 20%;">Null Hypothesis</th> <th style="width: 20%;">Test</th> <th style="width: 10%;">Sig.</th> <th style="width: 10%;">Decision</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>The distribution of Level of Satisfaction with online learning is the same across categories of Gender.</td> <td>Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test</td> <td>.468</td> <td>Retain the null hypothesis.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p style="font-size: small;">Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.</p>		Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision	1	The distribution of Level of Satisfaction with online learning is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.468	Retain the null hypothesis.	Accepted
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision								
1	The distribution of Level of Satisfaction with online learning is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.468	Retain the null hypothesis.								

There is no significant relationship between Gender and influence on ability to learn due to COVID 19	<p style="text-align: center;">Hypothesis Test Summary</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;"></th> <th style="width: 30%;">Null Hypothesis</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Test</th> <th style="width: 10%;">Sig.</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Decision</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td>The distribution of Covid-19 affected the ability to learn is the same across categories of Gender .</td> <td>Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test</td> <td style="text-align: center;">.878</td> <td>Retain the null hypothesis.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.</p>		Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision	1	The distribution of Covid-19 affected the ability to learn is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.878	Retain the null hypothesis.	Accepted
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision								
1	The distribution of Covid-19 affected the ability to learn is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.878	Retain the null hypothesis.								
There is no significant relationship between Gender and the willingness to continue offline learning	<p style="text-align: center;">Hypothesis Test Summary</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;"></th> <th style="width: 30%;">Null Hypothesis</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Test</th> <th style="width: 10%;">Sig.</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Decision</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td>The distribution of I wish to continue offline learning is the same across categories of Gender .</td> <td>Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test</td> <td style="text-align: center;">.005</td> <td style="background-color: yellow;">Reject the null hypothesis.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.</p>		Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision	1	The distribution of I wish to continue offline learning is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.005	Reject the null hypothesis.	Rejected
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision								
1	The distribution of I wish to continue offline learning is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.005	Reject the null hypothesis.								
There is no significant relationship between Gender and the benefits derived due to use of PPTs during online learning	<p style="text-align: center;">Hypothesis Test Summary</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;"></th> <th style="width: 30%;">Null Hypothesis</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Test</th> <th style="width: 10%;">Sig.</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Decision</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td>The distribution of Use of PPTs by teacher is beneficial is the same across categories of Gender .</td> <td>Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test</td> <td style="text-align: center;">.497</td> <td>Retain the null hypothesis.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.</p>		Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision	1	The distribution of Use of PPTs by teacher is beneficial is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.497	Retain the null hypothesis.	Accepted
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision								
1	The distribution of Use of PPTs by teacher is beneficial is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.497	Retain the null hypothesis.								
There is no significant relationship between Gender and influence of Home environment towards online learning	<p style="text-align: center;">Hypothesis Test Summary</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;"></th> <th style="width: 30%;">Null Hypothesis</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Test</th> <th style="width: 10%;">Sig.</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Decision</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td>The distribution of My home environment supports online learning is the same across categories of Gender .</td> <td>Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test</td> <td style="text-align: center;">.577</td> <td>Retain the null hypothesis.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.</p>		Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision	1	The distribution of My home environment supports online learning is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.577	Retain the null hypothesis.	Accepted
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision								
1	The distribution of My home environment supports online learning is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.577	Retain the null hypothesis.								
There is no significant relationship between Gender and use of white board towards online learning	<p style="text-align: center;">Hypothesis Test Summary</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;"></th> <th style="width: 30%;">Null Hypothesis</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Test</th> <th style="width: 10%;">Sig.</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Decision</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td>The distribution of Use of Virtual white board during online teaching is the same across categories of Gender .</td> <td>Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test</td> <td style="text-align: center;">.713</td> <td>Retain the null hypothesis.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.</p>		Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision	1	The distribution of Use of Virtual white board during online teaching is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.713	Retain the null hypothesis.	Accepted
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision								
1	The distribution of Use of Virtual white board during online teaching is the same across categories of Gender .	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.713	Retain the null hypothesis.								

II For the Second null hypothesis – Colleges and level of satisfaction of students towards online learning

H₀: - There is no significant relationship between College and level of satisfaction with online learning

H₁: - There is significant relationship between College and level of satisfaction with online learning

Level of Satisfaction with online learning

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	6.060	9	.673	.645	.757
Within Groups	146.133	140	1.044		
Total	152.193	149			

It was observed from the given data the F value is 0.645 and the significant value is 0.757 which is greater than 0.05. Hence, we reject our Null Hypothesis and state that There is significant relationship between College and level of satisfaction with online learning. That means the students of different colleges have different level of satisfaction. This can be further analysed by post-hoc.

Findings

It was found that

- Of the respondent 61.3% (92) were female where as 38.7 % (58) were Male.
- Equal numbers of 15 respondents were there from all the Colleges.
- Of the respondent, 58% were satisfied and only 12.7% respondents were dissatisfied and 29.3% were Neutral towards satisfaction derived from online learning.
- Of the respondent 55.3% Agreed that due to COVID-19 there was an impact on their learning process while 28% were Neutral about their opinion whereas 16.7% respondents were of the opinion that they did not faced any problems
- of the respondent 27.3% were neutral about the mode of learning they wish to adopt in coming future while 34% agreed they wish to continue offline learning in coming time period whereas 38.6% were of the opinion that they wish to continue online learning in coming time period too.
- of the respondent 75.4% Agreed that usage of PPTs by faculty during online lectures is quite helpful for them while only 6.7% respondents felt that usage of PowerPoint during online lectures is not good and 18% were neutral in this regards.
- of the respondent 70.6% were Satisfied with usage of white board during online teaching while 23.3% were neutral where as just 6% were Highly Dissatisfied.
- of the respondent 62.7% were Satisfied towards learning the syllabus through online medium where as 20.7% were Neutral towards same. While 16.7% respondents were Dissatisfied
- of the respondent 69.3% were satisfied with their home atmosphere while they were attending online lectures where as only 14% respondents were Dissatisfied and 16.7% were neutral.
- Of the respondents 54.7% were of the opinion that they wish to continue virtual method of learning in near future where as 45.3% wanted to move back to offline method of learning

- of the respondent 84% opined that they had Good connectivity at home while 16% respondents opined that they faced very poor connectivity at their home while attending online lectures.
- All the null hypothesis in the first set were accepted except one. That There is no significant relationship between Gender and the willingness to continue offline learning, but very marginally.
- The second null hypothesis also gets rejected indicating that There is significant relationship between College and level of satisfaction with online learning

Suggestions/ Measures

- The positive aspects/ suggestions to the Teachers
- Teaching and learn from anywhere and everywhere.
- Record the lectures and upload on YouTube or personal website
- Provide material to students on Google classroom or blogs or college website/ public domain
- Initially the knowledge of the teacher, his/ her teaching methodology was restricted to a particular college or to a particular area but by using virtual platforms now anyone can go through the recorded lectures and can attend online lectures i.e border less teaching and learning.
- More use of virtual white board
- More often, actual websites or live demonstration from the respective areas
- Use of PPT, animations, self-explanatory slides, etc
- Question-answers in between to track if the students understand the concept

Suggestions to the students

- As it is from anywhere, no physical presence is required, the absenteeism should be negligible.
- More focused and attention
- Participation would help the teacher to identify and solve the queries
- Respect the teacher and the hard work put in.

Suggestions to the Management/ Government

- State –of-the-art technology to be made available
- ICT enabled infrastructure to be provided
- The internet connectivity and speed to be improved across urban and rural areas
- Emphasis on training to teachers and students
- Motivation and morale boosting for the teachers and students

Significance of the study

Many opportunities have come up in the field of education; replaced books by PDF's, Replaced Classroom by Google classroom Whiteboard with Virtual board. Teacher and students use various platform for teaching and learning purpose Assignments replaced by various attachments. Universities has implemented online teaching and learning in an attempt to save the academic year of the students and to adapt the demand of the current situation. As all these has been done keeping the focus on the students. Hence, the students' satisfaction does play an important role

Discussion

College going is the best policy tool to enhance skills of the students by socially interacting with other students and

teachers. Interruption which is caused by the recent global crisis in students learning, destruction in internal and external assessments and cancellations of assessment and continuous postponement impacted student learning ability. Schedule of students and teachers has been destroyed and delayed. Universities have reframed their academic calendar cut down most of the holidays and vacations to cover up the loss which is caused. Temporary closure of college in the initial stage of spread the educator and the students had to shift towards the online teaching and learning platforms from face to face traditional method of teaching. Somehow this emergency situation is tackled with the help of technology. More research is needed in the area of education that would cover all the levels from school to higher education, from teachers to students and also all stakeholders and this also opens research avenues for interdisciplinary research covering economic aspect, psychology, etc.

Conclusion

Teachers cannot be replaced by Computer, Though, computers is an essential teaching aid for the teachers in this world of technologies in general and digital India, in particular. Indian teachers and students need to identify and acquaint themselves with the online teaching learning methodology and modalities, Though difficult in the initial phase, the duo have survived and got acquainted really faster than expected; this will go a long way in the field of education. This modus operandi should prove as a pilot study for the entire project of new education- Digital India. .

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